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Research Article

**STUDY OF EFFICACY OF MISOPROSTOL IN REDUCED
DOSE VIA VAGINAL ROUTE IN FIRST TRIMESTER
ABORTION**¹Dr.Mahe talat, ² Maimunah Faruque Malik, ³ Dr Nuzhat kanwal¹ Ameer-ud-din Medical College² Ameer -Ud-Din Medical College³ Quaid e Azam medical College bwp**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

Objective-The objective of this study is to analyze minimized side effect in first trimester absorption via vaginal route in reduced dose of misoprostol.

Methodology- First 200mg dose of mifepristone is given to the patients orally then after 24hours dose of misoprostol 400mg is given by intra vaginal and then after that 24 hours oral dose of vaginal misoprostol was given to the patients.

Findings- For this study 140 women were selected to examine them, out of these women 134 had total fetus removal after finishing of the treatment routine, and achievement pace of 95.7% was accomplished.

Conclusion- The dose of misoprostol that was given vaginally after the dose of 200mg of mifepristone orally, and it was observed that this has reduced side effects and powerful outcome for restorative fetus removal in first trimester premature birth.

Keywords: First trimester absorption, mifepristone, misoprostol

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INTRODUCTION:

In gynecological department in a tertiary care hospital in Lahore , the procedure which is commonly performed is called abortion. To terminate the pregnancy various surgical instruments are used, there are a lot of complications associated with this procedure for example perforation of uterine, stop bleeding, and avoid the products which might be a reason due to which women cannot be able to conceive again. So nowadays for abortion purpose use of medical procedure instead of the use of surgical instruments is more in use. There are some medical procedure for example the use of misoprostol and mifepristone is frequently done for the first termination of pregnancy. The alternative procedure of surgical methods for the termination of pregnancy is medical procedure which is very important and in this pregnancy is terminated in its early stages through proper medication. According the world health organization the use of 200mg mifepristone and 24hours after taking the mifepristone, the use of misoprostol has very reduced side effects when it use for the termination of pregnancy in its starting days.

When mifepristone is given orally then in reaction it stops the receptors of progesterone and its process, through this on myometrium the sensitivity of prostaglandins also increases. This contract the uterine regularly, as the ripening action of mifepristone is cervical thus it is very helpful to terminate the pregnancy. Due to the pros of medical procedures in termination of pregnancy along with their efficiency and reduced side effects this procedure is getting more and more popularity to terminate pregnancy in early days and also due to the easiness in taking the medical procedures. Many studies have been done for observing the effectiveness and reduced side effects of medical treatment. According to some studies the oral dose of 600mg of mifepristone and up to 48 hours after the dose 400mg dose of misoprostol is resulted in the complete abortion. Likewise in some studies the same kind of results were deduced by using the low dose of mifepristone. In some studies to inject misoprostol alternative routes were also used like vaginal, buccal etc. but for this procedure the duration was increased and this procedure also has an advantage that it does not affect the metabolism of liver. The bioavailability when dose was given

through vaginal was greater than it was taken orally. Vaginal injection of mifepristone has relatively a higher success rate than the mifepristone that was taken orally. The severe side effect can be minimized by taking the reduced dose of mifepristone vaginally. The use of mifepristone and its route to use to terminate the pregnancy in its early day is directly related to the side effects than can occur after this procedure for example nausea, pin due to the contraction of uterine and pain in abdomen.

METHODOLOGY:

In this total 176 women was selected who wanted to terminate their pregnancy in their early days and in very first stage to confirm their pregnancy ultrasonography was done on all the selected women. In this all those women were excluded who were found in any kind of complication like suspicion of threatened abortion, ectopic pregnancy or any other problem related to health , those women who were conceiving from more than the 9 weeks were also excluded. A written consent agreement were signed from all the women. All the expected complication and advantages of medical procedure and in case of any failure in medical procedure the necessity of surgical method was thoroughly explained with all the women. First 200mg dose of mifepristone is given to the patients orally then after 24hours dose of misoprostol 400mg is given by intra vaginal and then after that 24 hours oral dose of vaginal misoprostol was given to the patients. Those women which were enrolled under this medical procedure were informed to visit their doctor after five days, so that all the clinical examination and side effects can be examined. Ultrasonography was also done to check the complete abortion. Patient who had incomplete abortion were asked to come again after seven days to check the side effect of medical procedure. Patient with complete abortion were categorize success of treatment and patient who faced incomplete abortion were categorized as treatment failure.

RESULT:

In this study total 176 patients were enrolled in which 22 did not meet the research criteria so this study was done on 154 women.

Table 1: showing age and their Percentage

S. No.	Age of women (Years)	No. of Patients	Percentage
1	18-20	11	7.9%
2	21-24	40	28.6%
3	25-30	54	38.6%
4	31-35	25	17.8%
5	36-40	10	7.1%

This table showed that most of the selected women were lying between the 25 to 30 years old and second higher age group of women were between the 21 to 30 years and least number of selected women were lying in 36 to 40 who wanted to abort.

Table 2: Distribution of Perceiving age and their percentage

S. No.	Age of gestation (weeks)	No. of Patient	Percentage
1	< 5 weeks	32	22.9%
2	< 6 weeks	63	45.0%
3	< 7 weeks	27	19.3%
4	< 8 weeks	10	7.1%
5	< 9 weeks	8	5.7%

Table 2 is showing that most of the women who were selected for medical abortion had the pregnancy age less than 6 weeks

Table 3: showing treatment success percentage

S. No.	Age of gestation (weeks)	Complete Abortion	Percentage	Total success
1	< 5 weeks	32	100%	95.7%
2	< 6 weeks	62	98.4%	
3	< 7 weeks	26	96.3%	
4	< 8 weeks	8	80%	
5	< 9 weeks	6	75%	

This table showed the lower the pregnancy age greater will be the success rate of medical treatment. Out of 154 women 134 had the complete abortion and the percentage of the treatment success was 95.7%.

No severe side effect was observed in this process except some women who suffered heavy bleeding for more than seven years during medical procedure.

DISCUSSION:

For observing the effectiveness and reduced side effects of medical treatment, many studies have been done. According to some studies the oral dose of 600mg of mifepristone and up to 48 hours after the dose 400mg dose of misoprostol is resulted in the complete abortion. Likewise in some studies the same

results were collected by using the low dose of mifepristone. In some studies alternative routes were also used like vaginal, buccal etc. to inject misoprostol, but for this procedure the duration was increased and the advantage of this procedure is that it does not affect the metabolism of liver.

Most of the selected women for this study were lying between the 25 to 30 years old and second higher age group of women were between the 21 to 30 years and least number of selected women were lying in 36 to 40 who wanted to abort. For this study 140 women were selected to examine them, out of these women 134 had total fetus removal after finishing of the treatment routine, and achievement pace of 95.7% was accomplished. First 200mg dose of mifepristone is given to the patients orally then after 24 hours dose of misoprostol 400mg is given by intra vaginal and then after that 24 hours oral dose of vaginal misoprostol was given to the patients. The viability of this system is tantamount with different investigations and unfriendly impacts were definitely decreased. The high portion of misoprostol causes increasingly side effects. (12) So high portion of Misoprostol ought to be kept away from.

The ladies who need to evade dilatation and curettage, for example careful mediation utilizes therapeutic fetus removal and feels fulfilled paying little mind to the routine utilized. In our examination likewise 95% of ladies were happy with our system. The utilization of misoprostol 400 mg vaginally is increasingly successful and with lesser symptoms.

CONCLUSION:

The first dose of misoprostol was given vaginally after the dose of 200mg of mifepristone orally, and it was observed that this has reduced side effects and powerful outcome for restorative fetus removal in first trimester premature birth

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